

Trust, Types & Transparency: TIC-TAC-TOE

Working Paper v01.00

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Introduction

The goal of the FIDELIS project is to establish a European network of FAIR-enabling trustworthy digital repositories and to support their EOSC federation. The project and the future Network needs to better understand the repository landscape and stakeholders. Populating the Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM)¹ has implications for alignment, interoperability, assessment and assistance within the Network and beyond.

The 'superset' of 30 Metadata and Data Services Activities/Functions (MaDSAF²) is used in the FIDELIS project's TTRAM. The TTRAM looks at how different factors act as variables on the activities and functions (A|F) and how they influence the types of information (like policies and metadata) that could or should be made transparent. The initial variables are the levels of retention, curation and preservation being offered by repositories, and an exploration of repository 'types'.

This draft working paper looks at the next steps for the Network and the Matrix, and what level of additional detail is required to make progress, taking account of:

1. Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) status is assigned based on different criteria, making it clear that trust is contextual rather than binary.
2. More details than *repository-type* and *level of retention, curation and preservation* are needed to meaningfully categorise repositories
3. Understanding the context and the 'types' of repositories provide input to specific recommendations about what information should be made transparent to support assessments of trustworthiness.

There are different assumptions and expectations around 'Trustworthy Digital Repositories' . These include the CoreTrustSeal³ (all active preservation), the European Commission⁴ (funded project outputs) and the EOSC⁵ (engagement with EOSC Nodes). These variant perspectives on trust make it clear that we must clarify and define their context.

This paper explores possible categories of Digital Object Venue Entities (DOVE, see [appendix](#)) in terms of their coverage, forte, levels of curation, and A|F. Their relevance and application in different trust contexts clarifies what information about DOVEs and their digital objects should be made transparent.

¹ FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v01.00 Guide (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17144141>

² L'Hours, H., Bell, D., & Parkes, O. (2025). Metadata and Data Services Activities-Functions MaDSAF Overview (v02.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17779868>

³ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 (V01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012>

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

⁵ EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

TIC: Trust in Context

For any prescriptive criteria it is essential to understand the context in which they will be applied. The broad context can be refined to consider the [types and categories](#) of entities that criteria will be applied to, and the [transparent objects and entities](#) needed to support compliance assessments.

Trust Targets

To assess trustworthiness, as for any other evaluation, we must understand the scope of the entities we are examining. In this paper we refer to 'repositories' in the broadest sense, but any venue where a user (human or machine) interacts with digital objects' data and metadata is in scope. Each DOVE can be described in terms of the characteristics of the relevant *organisation(s)* and their *catalogue(s) of objects*. This can also support a clearer understanding of the permissions, prohibitions and obligations⁶ attached to different human actors and machine agents.

Trust Authorities

Understanding the trust context also depends on clarity about the identity and motivations of specific actors. An authority body needs to be identified for each of:

- The **Criteria** - their authorship, change, versioning and release.
- The **Assessment Process** - evaluation methods, outcomes, terms and how they change.
- **Status** - how it is assigned after assessment against criteria, and how it might be revoked.

In the case of the CoreTrustSeal the Trust Target is "any active preservation repository" and the CoreTrustSeal Board (drawn from the community of certified repositories) acts as the authority body over Criteria, Assessment Process and Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) status.

In the cases of the EOSC the Trust Target is 'a repository onboarding to a node'⁷ and the authority for assigning TDR status is the EOSC Association. The EOSC Handbook⁸ confers authority over the criteria and assessment process to third parties:

"Trustworthy, by implementing the requirements for trustworthy data repositories, preferably certified by a community-endorsed certification scheme such as CoreTrustSeal⁹, Nestor Seal¹⁰ or ISO 16363¹¹ certification."¹²

⁶ Cf: terms used in the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

⁷ E.g. the EC Node: <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

⁸ EOSC Association. (2026). EOSC Federation Handbook (2.0). EOSC Association. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18454649>

⁹, <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

¹⁰ https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/EN/Zertifizierung/nestor_Siegel/nestor_siegel_node.html

¹¹ Equivalent to Recommended practice CCSDS 652.0-M-1 from the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/652x0m1.pdf>

¹² EOSC Federation Handbook (2.0) EOSC Association. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18454649> (5.2.2 Research Data Sources) pp49.

Guidance on where EC project outputs should be deposited are provided by the EC Annotated Grant Agreement (EC AGA)¹³, which divides repositories into three categories:

1. “certified repositories, such as those certified by international organisations or government-authorised certification bodies (e.g. CoreTrustSeal, nestor Seal DIN31644, ISO16363)
2. disciplinary or domain repositories commonly used and endorsed by the research communities, and which are recognised internationally
3. general-purpose repositories, institutional repositories or any other repositories that present the essential characteristics of trusted repositories”

The first case mirrors the EOSC approach, but no associated criteria for “commonly used and endorsed” or “recognised internationally” are provided for option two. A set of criteria are provided for option 3, but with no associated assessment process by which trustworthy status can be conferred.

The scenarios above are important, but represent only a small number of the criteria (policies, standards etc) that repositories are expected to comply with by different authorities to demonstrate their trustworthiness.

Understanding the relevant entities and authorities above, and identifying the relevant types and categories (TAC below) help us to understand the trust context. This provides a necessary basis for identifying the transparent characteristics of objects and other entities (TOE, below) needed to support assessment in a given context.

TAC: Types & Categories

Repositories are commonly referred to by type, including institutional, national, disciplinary and generic¹⁴. These terms will continue to be used, but we propose that defining trust in context for a DOVE depends on more specific categorisation by coverage (depositors, users and objects), forte (from generic to specialist, including disciplines and content specialists such as audio/visual) and the levels of retention, curation and active preservation (LoRCAP) provided. In TTRAM, these all act as variables on the repository activities and functions (A|F), which influences the information that needs to be made transparent.

Coverage: Depositors, ReUsers and Catalogues of Objects

If a DOVE self-describes as national (or regional, or any other restricted geographical coverage), then what does that imply? Do they mainly focus on depositors from one nation? Do they specifically exclude depositors from others? The same applies to the ReUsers of digital objects. Or are the restrictions based on the objects themselves? Does the research have to be funded by the geography in scope? Or does the data need to be relevant to the geography in scope?

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

¹⁴ E.g. see property ID8 under the re3data schema:

https://gfzpublic.gfz.de/rest/items/item_5022309_8/component/file_5022681/content

Similar questions about inclusion and exclusion of depositors, objects and reusers apply to disciplinary and institutional coverage.

These categories are highly relevant to researcher questions including “Where can I (researcher of Type X) deposit my digital object (of type A)” and “where can I (researcher of Type Y) access digital objects (of Type B)” .

Forte: from Generic to Specialist

A generic DOVE, or even a domain DOVE may not have enough detailed and specific metadata to support granular *disciplinary* methodologies. A disciplinary DOVE may not be able to scale to very large objects, or may not provide high level metadata designed to be harvested by more generic systems.

The word forte¹⁵ is chosen to focus on the strengths of different DOVEs. Specialities are not limited to discipline or domain. For example, a general purpose publisher may have specific expertise in pdf formats. Specialist research methodologies, including statistical analyses or surveys are relevant across many disciplines. DOVEs that specialise in audio-visual digital objects may need guidance on descriptive metadata from other specialities (e.g. disciplines). Many disciplinary and generic DOVEs also hold audio-video data and would benefit from guidance from A/V specialists.

Understanding these categories is a necessary precursor for meaningful conversations about cross, inter, and multi-disciplinary research, objects or repositories. A researcher seeking to deposit or access data would benefit from understanding the forte of a repository.

Levels of Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP)

Understanding the coverage and forte of a DOVE does not tell us everything we need to know about the knowledge and skills a repository will require. This will be influenced by the levels of ‘care’ a DOVE provides to digital objects. The CoreTrustSeal levels of retention, curation and active preservation (LoRCAP) emerged as a way to help clarify which applicants are in scope for their certification.

The LoRCAP divides tiers of service that offer reliable retention, dependable deposit, curation quality and active preservation (paraphrased from the original). These can be cumulative, i.e. an **active preservation** repository that undertakes to ensure digital objects remain accessible and usable for the long term may also ensure integrity-driven **retention** with clear time parameters, apply **deposit compliance** rules (e.g. restricted file formats, or minimal metadata), and offer **initial curation** to ensure digital objects meet defined criteria. If a DOVE does less than this it is still playing a significant role and meeting real demand.

Clarity on the levels of curation and preservation provided are significant for depositors, reusers and funders to understand how a DOVE with particular fortes cares for digital objects.

¹⁵ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/forte#>

Types and Categories as Activities/Function Variables

The MaDSAF¹⁶ list is a 'superset' of 30 activities and functions (A|F) based on a review of existing criteria used by the FIDELIS 'trustworthy transparent repository attributes matrix'. In line with multiple existing criteria¹⁷, it divides activities and functions (A|F) into: digital object management, organisational infrastructure, technology and security.

The coverage, forte and levels above act as variables on how a DOVE undertakes different activities and functions. If an A|F is 'not applicable' to a DOVE then this is important to categorisation. For example, if a DOVE provides a retention-only service then the 'curation, quality, compliance' A|F will not be relevant to any trust context.

In many contexts the A|F will be relevant to Trust, this can only be demonstrated and assessed if appropriate information about objects, DOVEs and other entities is made transparent.

TOE: Transparent Objects/Entities

For any DOVE, moving information from an individual's knowledge to a shared document will reduce organisational risk. Documented information will support consistency of practice in an activity or function whatever the coverage, forte or levels of preservation provided. Coherent and aligned management of documentation (standards, policies, procedures, metadata) will improve overall maturity. Some information will need to be formalised and published for the benefit of depositors, reusers, funders, peers and other interested parties.

Being transparent about information doesn't necessarily mean making it entirely public, but fully open information has the broadest potential for benefit. Some information used as evidence in evaluations may only need to be shared with the assessor.

Making any assessment, including of trustworthiness, depends on understanding the relevant context. For DOVEs this includes their coverage, forte and offered levels of curation and preservation, which influence the activities and functions they undertake.

¹⁶ Originally prepared to support UKDS discussions around compliance and the UKRI/ESRC Future Data Services Programme.

¹⁷ E.g. CoreTrustSeal and ISO16363

Appendix: DOVEs (Digital Object Venue Entities)

Trust related terms are not consistent across the formal 'TDR' standards. DIN31644, the Nestor Seal refers to 'Trustworthy Digital Archives', CoreTrustSeal to 'Trustworthy Digital Repositories' and 'Trustworthy Repositories'. The 'family' of CCSDS/ISO Standards use the terms [Archive](#), [Trustworthy Digital Repository](#) and [Long Term Use](#). The EDEN project proposes to use 'Trustworthy Digital Archive' for entities that adopt and deliver their *Core Preservation Processes*.

The European Commission¹⁸ assigns trust status based on community endorsement and its' own *essential characteristics*, while the EOSC Federation¹⁹ has not yet established a formal policy for implementing trustworthiness of research data sources (including both repositories and databases). All of these are potential members for the FIDELIS Network, but there are wider groups of relevant stakeholders (and possible members) including Trusted Research Environment (TRE), EOSC Nodes and Technical Repository Service Providers (TRSP).

Digital Object Venue²⁰ Entities (DOVEs) are simply any environment where any human actor or machine agent might interact with (store, care for, search for, access, reuse etc) one or more digital objects. DOVEs are inclusive of entities called repositories, archives and databases, but also trusted research environments (TRE) and EOSC Nodes. The term also covers registries (primarily focussing on metadata records about objects held elsewhere) and Technical Repository Service Providers (TRSP) that provide ancillary and supporting technologies and associated services to other DOVEs. As well as being inclusive, the acronym avoids potential discussion and debate about the exact meaning of repository vs archive etc. Instead it lets us describe different entities based on specific types, categories and trust contexts. Defining a particular DOVE depends on information about the organisation(s), catalogue(s) (of objects and services) and the objects involved.

Dove means 'where' in Italian, but we're also interested in exploring the who, what, when, why and how of DOVEs.

Organisations

One or more organisations or parts of an organisation involved in some way with a catalogue of digital objects.

Because there is some debate and variance in approach about whether 'a repository' is an organisation, part of an organisation, or simply a catalogue of objects, we address 'organisation' separately in this DOVE model.

¹⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

¹⁹ EOSC Association. (2026). EOSC Federation Handbook (2.0). EOSC Association. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18454649>

²⁰ The term 'venue' is used more broadly than, but in line with, that of the OSTRAILS projects Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF). Miksa, T., Wilkinson, M., Manghi, P., & Suchánek, M. (2025). D1.4 OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V1. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795000>

Example Scenario: The ESRC (org) funded UK Data Service (org) is a partnership between multiple universities (orgs). The UK Data Archive (org) is a partner in the UK Data Service (org) but also a department (org) within the social science faculty (org) of the University of Essex (org). Each 'org' in the previous sentences has some relevant rights and roles as actors involved in one or more catalogues. It's important that we can differentiate them and attach relevant metadata to them about their roles, rights and responsibilities in a DOVE, including whether they're a legal entity.

Addressing organisations distinctly allows us to differentiate them as actors with responsibilities in digital object management, but also to refer to relevant connected organisation such as standards bodies, assessment providers, networks and umbrella organisations.

Catalogues

The term catalogue is used to refer to anything from printed lists to software that supports resource discovery and access functionality. DCAT²¹, an "RDF vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between data catalogs" covers 'datasets' and 'data services'. In the DOVE context a catalogue is a list of metadata records describing digital objects or services.

Services

Including services allows us to associate objects and related services (e.g. [dcat:servesDataset](#) is "a collection of data that this data service can distribute"), but potentially also to include a wider range of services offered by a DOVE, including technical repository service providers, e.g. in FitSM²² a service catalogue is a "customer-facing list of all live services offered along with relevant information about these services".

(Digital) Objects

Sometimes TDR is used to stand for 'trustworthy data repositories', and sometimes 'data' is used in a broad sense to be inclusive of anything 'digital'. Many, but not all, DOVEs focus on various raw and processed 'data' of relevance to researchers and/or created/collected during the course of research. However, in this model all data and metadata objects are included under the term 'digital object'.

Some catalogues hold metadata records about physical objects, from researchers to blood samples. Others hold records about digital objects including datasets, software [needs canonical inclusive list from both EDEN and FIDELIS]. Some DOVEs manage the objects referenced from their catalogues (e.g. repositories), while others manage metadata about objects held by others (e.g. registries).

²¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

²² https://training.ni4os.eu/pluginfile.php/2862/mod_resource/content/0/FitSM_Guide_Identifying_Services_v1.0.pdf